

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INTEGRATION OF SATELLITE DATA INTO MARITIME FLEET MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS

Korostin O.

Classic Private University, Ukraine

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13737326>

Abstract

This article analyzes the integration of satellite data into maritime fleet management systems. It discusses the features of using satellite and Automatic Identification System (AIS) data for managing and monitoring maritime fleets. The article emphasizes the importance of a combined approach to ensure comprehensive coverage, enhance data accuracy, and optimize maritime operations.

Keywords: *satellite data, Automatic Identification System (AIS), maritime fleet management, vessel monitoring, maritime safety, operational efficiency, technology integration, marine navigation.*

Introduction

Managing a maritime fleet is a complex task that requires the coordination of numerous factors to ensure the safe and efficient execution of marine operations. Given the increasing volume of maritime transport and the growing number of vessels, effective management becomes particularly important for preventing incidents, enhancing operational efficiency, and optimizing operational costs. In recent decades, advancements in technologies such as satellite systems and automatic identification systems (AIS) have significantly expanded the capabilities of maritime fleet management, providing new tools for monitoring and data analysis.

Satellite data (SD) have become an essential tool in maritime fleet management systems due to their global coverage and high accuracy. Thanks to AIS, which enables the automatic transmission of information about a vessel's location, speed, and course, real-time tracking becomes feasible. However, despite the considerable advantages of both systems, relying on just one of them may have its limitations. Only the integration of data obtained from satellites and AIS represents a crucial step toward creating more accurate and reliable maritime fleet management systems. Combining information from both sources allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the current state of the maritime environment and vessel movements. The aim of this article is to analyze the impact of SD and AIS on maritime fleet management.

Main part

Maritime fleet management systems comprise a complex array of technologies and processes aimed at effective planning, coordination, and control of maritime vessel operations. They include a variety of tools for monitoring and tracking vessels, ensuring safety, managing traffic, and planning routes.

Such systems integrate data on vessel locations, weather conditions, and environmental status to optimize navigation and prevent accidents. They utilize satellite technologies, AIS, and software for data analysis and decision-making [1]. These systems assist not only in managing shipping and ensuring safety but also in reducing operational costs and minimizing environmental impact. Innovations in technology contribute to improving the accuracy and efficiency of fleet management. The evolution of developments in this field continues, striving to enhance the sustainability of maritime transport and the safety of maritime operations, making them essential for the modern maritime industry.

Satellite data for fleet monitoring

Monitoring and managing maritime fleets rely heavily on the crucial role played by SD. They provide information that helps enhance the safety, efficiency, and resilience of maritime operations. This data can include a variety of information collected through different sensors and technologies, and it is used in a wide range of applications (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Types of SD

Optical images are used to obtain high-quality photographs and maps that can display surface details of the Earth, including ships, ports, and weather conditions. They are particularly useful for analyzing and assessing current conditions. **Radar data** are collected using radars mounted on satellites and can provide information about weather conditions, such as cloud cover and precipitation levels. **Infrared data** serve to measure the temperature of surfaces and clouds [2]. These data can assist in weather forecasting and detecting marine anomalies.

Satellite systems enable **real-time tracking** of vessel locations, helping to monitor their movements and respond promptly to changes in routes. Satellites provide **meteorological data**, which are crucial for planning safe and efficient routes, preventing accidents, and ensuring comfortable conditions for the crew. They can also **monitor pollution**, such as oil spills, changes in water temperature, and other environmental parameters. This aids in timely responses to ecological incidents and protects the marine ecosystem [3].

The **coordination** of vessel movements, prevention of collisions, and management of traffic in busy maritime routes and ports are facilitated by SD. The use of historical data on vessel movements allows for traffic analysis, identification of potential issues, and improved route planning. SD are a vital part of modern maritime fleet management systems, contributing to enhanced efficiency, safety, and resilience.

Automatic identification system

The AIS technology is designed for the exchange of information between vessels and shore stations. It transmits data regarding the location, speed, course, and other characteristics of vessels in real time. The functioning principle of AIS is based on radio communication and data transmission between vessels and shore stations. Each vessel equipped with AIS has a transmitter that regularly sends data about its location, speed, direction, type, and other characteristics. This data is generated automatically and transmitted at specific intervals. The information is broadcasted on a designated radio frequency (usually in the VHF range), allowing other vessels and shore stations to receive this data [4]. The transmission occurs in the form of messages containing various parameters, such as the vessel's identification number (MMSI), speed, course, and status.

Vessels within range can receive AIS messages from other ships. This enables captains to see the location and movement of nearby vessels, which enhances their understanding of the navigational environment. Shore stations also receive AIS data, allowing them to monitor vessel movements in the waters and manage

maritime traffic. These stations can process the information and relay it to control centers. The integration of AIS with other systems, such as electronic maps, marine management systems and meteorological services, increases the overall efficiency of navigation.

Thus, AIS represents a powerful tool that ensures automated and efficient information exchange between vessels and shore stations, enhancing safety and awareness in the maritime environment.

Integration of satellite and AIS data

An important aspect of maritime fleet management is the integration of satellite and AIS data. This process involves combining technologies that provide reliable vessel tracking and enhance safety at sea. SD allow for real-time information on vessel locations, ensuring global coverage even in the most remote areas. The use of AIS for data exchange between ships and shore stations contributes to more efficient traffic management on waterways.

The combination of these technologies significantly improves monitoring accuracy, increases responsiveness to situational changes, and reduces incident risks. This process is carried out in several stages. In the first stage, data collection takes place. Information from AIS is transmitted by vessels in real time using AIS technology. SD are obtained from satellites equipped with radars and other sensors. The next stage involves the transmission and reception of data. The data received by the AIS is transmitted using radio signals at frequencies 161.975 MHz and 162.025 MHz between ships and shore stations. SD are transmitted through satellite communication channels to ground stations. Following this, the received information undergoes processing and analysis [5]. The data obtained by the AIS is analyzed to obtain information about traffic, possible collisions and navigation. SD are processed for more accurate vessel location determination, weather monitoring, and broad area surveillance.

The satellite and AIS data are integrated into a single system to obtain a comprehensive picture of the maritime situation. Integration may include the combination of vessel location data, courses, and speeds, as well as information on weather conditions and potential obstacles [6]. The integrated data are displayed on navigation system screens and vessel traffic management (VTS) systems. This allows operators and crew members to have a complete understanding of the current maritime situation.

The integration of satellite and AIS data represents a powerful approach to monitoring and managing maritime fleets. The combination of these two important sources of information offers numerous advantages for creating a complete and more accurate picture of vessel statuses and maritime conditions (table 1).

Comparison of the main approaches to marine fleet management systems [7,8]

Type of data	Advantages	Disadvantages
Satellite data	Global coverage; independence from ground infrastructure; can provide additional information.	High cost; limited update frequency; need for powerful computing resources for data processing and analysis.
AIS data	Real-time: data on vessel movement changes is received instantly; relatively low cost; suitable for local monitoring and traffic management in ports and coastal areas.	Limited coverage; risk of counterfeiting: data can be easily falsified or altered; dependence on transmitter activity.
Integration of satellite and AIS data	Provides more comprehensive coverage and improved monitoring accuracy; enhanced real-time and update frequency by combining data sources; increased reliability and accuracy of information through cross-verification of data from different sources.	Complexity of integration requires sophisticated processing and synchronization of various data types; increased storage and processing requirements due to large data volumes; compatibility issues with data formats and standards may require additional efforts.

In summary of the advantages and disadvantages of satellite and AIS data, it can be noted that each of these solutions brings its strengths to maritime traffic monitoring. The integration of satellite and AIS data allows for compensating the shortcomings of each system, providing a more comprehensive and reliable solution. This holistic approach improves operational management and safety at sea, reducing the risks of incidents and ensuring economic benefits through resource optimization and enhanced analytical capabilities. Despite the advantages of integration, the process of combining data can be complex and costly, requiring additional computing resources and technical support.

American companies are actively utilizing the integration of satellite and AIS data to optimize fleet management, enhance safety, and improve operational efficiency. For instance, **ACBL** employs satellite navigation systems to manage its barges on rivers and inland waterways. The use of GPS enables the company to track vessel movements and optimize their routes, which is especially important for ensuring safety on rivers with limited navigation conditions [9].

Royal Caribbean Cruises uses satellite systems for communication and real-time tracking of its vessels. This includes monitoring ship locations, managing routes, and ensuring communication with shore services. Satellite navigation aids in safety management and improves navigation processes, which is crucial for providing safe and comfortable travel for passengers [10].

These examples demonstrate how American companies successfully integrate satellite and AIS data to create more efficient and reliable maritime traffic monitoring systems. This approach ensures comprehensive coverage, enhances safety, and optimizes fleet management, particularly in remote and challenging environments.

Conclusions

The integration of SD into maritime fleet management systems represents a significant advancement in optimizing shipping and enhancing safety at sea. The use of satellite and AIS data allows companies not only to track vessel locations in real time but also to analyze

information on weather conditions, sea currents, and potential risks. This creates opportunities for more effective fleet management, reduces operational costs, and improves customer service.

Data integration systems help prevent collisions, respond to emergencies, and ensure compliance with international standards and regulations. Such solutions promote more sustainable use of marine resources and protect ecological systems.

Given the growing competition and demands for compliance with safety standards, the integration of satellite technologies will become an essential tool for shipowners and operators. Companies that adapt to these changes will not only enhance their efficiency but also secure leading positions in the market. In the future, we can expect further technological advancements that will make fleet management even more advanced and safer.

References:

- Burkov D. E. Application of Vessel Information Systems for Monitoring and Controlling the Technical Condition of Ship Equipment // Bulletin of the Admiral S. O. Makarov State University of Maritime and Inland Shipping. 2023. Vol. 15. No. 5. p. 893-902.
- Yuukin I. V. The Problem of Implementing the Concept of Maximum Integration of Heterogeneous Data in Practical Navigation // Bulletin of the Admiral S. O. Makarov State University of Maritime and Inland Shipping. 2024. Vol. 15. No. 6. p. 998-1014.
- Uliankina I. Methods and tools of strategic planning to enhance climate resilience of businesses in the USA // Innovacionnaya nauka. 2024. № 8-1. C. 51-56.
- Shving F. B. Modern Technologies and Integrated Observation Systems Are «Instrumental» for Fisheries Oceanography: A Brief History of Ocean Data Collection // Fisheries Oceanography. 2023. Vol. 32. No. 1. p. 28-69.

5. Park, S., Yang, K. S., Kim, J. U. Designing a Ship Data Warehouse Using Big Data Analysis Technology and Artificial Intelligence for Ship Monitoring Systems // Electronics. 2023. Vol. 12. No. 8. p. 1943.
6. Solovyev K. Developing sustainable business strategies in conditions of global economic uncertainties // Cold Science. 2024. № 4/2024. P. 41-49.
7. Tiumentsev D. Application of Cryptographic Technologies for Information Protection in Cloud Services // Stolypin Annals. 2024. Vol. 6. No. 3.
8. Kendjaev A. Features of Establishing Foreign Economic Activities When Entering the American Market: Practical Steps and Legal Nuances // Sciences of Europe. 2024. No. 144.p. 8-11.
9. Barge Transportation. Market Size and Share Analysis // URL: <https://www.coherentmarketinsights.com/industry-reports/barge-transportation-market> (date of application 25.07.2024).
10. Bukhalis D., Papathanasis A., Wafeidou M. Intelligent cruise: applications of intelligent technologies and their dissemination in cruise tourism // Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technologies. 2022. Vol. 13. No. 4. p. 626-649.